

Task Description

Imagine you got your first job as a journalist on a world news desk as a fact checker and production assistant. Your organization frequently covers Latin American protests and social movements. In particular, there is a focus on the recent Cuban Protests and their still ongoing effects. Use the provided system to better understand the roots of the Cuban Protests, related events, and the historical context so that you can begin contributing at your new job.

In particular, to guide you through this process, we provide you three tasks of increasing complexity. Please answer them using the provided system. Please comment on your thought process as you work through the tasks and use the tool to solve the problems.

Task 1: Warm-up Questions - Circle the correct answer [~10 minutes]:

- When did the protests start?
 - a) April 16th
 - b) May 1st
 - c) July 11th
 - d) July 17th
 - e) August 1st
- Who was the Cuban President at the time of the protests?
 - a) Raúl Castro
 - b) Miguel Diaz-Canel
 - c) Fidel Castro
 - d) Nicolas Maduro
 - e) Salvador Valdés-Mesa

Task 2: Analysis [~50 minutes]:

- Identify the **main causes** of the 2021 Cuban Protests.
- Identify the **effects** of the 2021 Cuban Protests.
- Provide all the **insights** that you can gather from this data.